

without abdominal chalkiness, and cook flaky with good volume expansion.

In blast (Bl) screening trials at Ponnampet, the Bl hotspot in Karnataka, Sona Mahsuri was moderately resistant, with an average rating of 2.5 compared with 5.9 for Intan (Table 1).

In 26 trials since 1980, Sona Mahsuri has yielded an average 5.8 t/ha. In 12 trials, it yielded 6.0 t/ha compared to 5.4 t for Jaya (Table 2). In 1981-83 field trials at 14 sites in Mandya and Mysore, Sona Mahsuri yielded an average 6.5 t/ha compared with 5.4 t/ha for Mahsuri. At 6 other sites, it yielded an average 7.5 t/ha compared with 6.9 t for Prakash (Table 3).

Sona Mahsuri is gaining popularity and may soon be released for cultivation. ☞

Table 2. Sona Mahsuri grain yield in yield trials at Mandya, 1980-84.

Year	Yield (t/ha)	
	Sona Mahsuri	Saya
1980	5.8	5.2
1982	6.1	6.0
1983	6.3	5.4
1984	5.8	5.0
Av	6.0	5.4

Table 3. Sona Mahsuri grain yield in farm trials at Mysore and Mandya.

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Sona Mahsuri	Check
		<i>Mahsuri</i>
1981	6.5	3.5
1982	7.0	6.5
1983	6.4	6.2
Av	6.6	5.4
		<i>Prakash</i>
1982	7.6	7.3
1984	7.5	6.6
Av	7.5	6.9

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IR13540-56-3-2-1: a promising rice for irrigated land in Bihar

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IR13540-56-3-2-1 (R. Heenati/ IR30 (BPHS)// IR2823-399-5) was chosen in 1981 kharif from the International Rice Yield Nursery - Medium. It matures in 130-135 d, is semidwarf, has good grain quality, and is suitable for irrigated, transplanted culture. IR13540-56-3-2-1 is moderately resistant to bacterial blight and will be a good substitute for Jaya and Sita, which have become susceptible.

In state trials from 1982 to 1984, IR13540-56-3-2-1 yielded consistently and 27% higher than Jaya and 20% more than Sita (Table 1, 2). It has been proposed for 1985 minikit trials in farmers' fields. ☞

Table 2. Mean yield of IR13540-56-3-2-1 and check varieties, 1982-84, Bihar, India.

Variety	Site					Mean
	Patna	Pusa	Sabour	Dhangain	Tilaundha	
	<i>Yield (t/ha)</i>					
IR13540-56-3-2-1	5.6	3.4	3.6	5.5	2.7	4.2
Jaya	3.7	3.1	2.6	4.4	2.6	3.3
Sita	3.8	2.9	3.0	4.9	2.7	3.5
	<i>Increase (%over Jaya)</i>					
IR 13540-56-3-2-1	51	10	38	23	4	27
	<i>Increase (%) over Sita</i>					
IR13540-56-3-2-1	47	17	20	12	0	20

Response of selected minikit rice varieties to nitrogen and tungro virus (RTV) on the Cauvery Delta

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Medium-duration IET7301, IET7303, IET7573, and IET7230 were compared with IR20 and Co 43 at TNRRI in Sep-Jan 1984. N was applied at 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha. There was widespread RTV incidence and varieties were scored for infection.

Soil was a clay loam with low available N, medium P and K, and pH

Table 1. Performance of IR1 3540-56-3-2-1 in state variety trials in Bihar, India.

Trial location	Grain yield (t/ha)			CD at 5%
	IR13540-56-3-2-1	Jaya	Sita	
	<i>1982 kharif</i>			
Patna	5.4	3.4	3.6	1.0
Pusa	4.0	3.4	3.3	—
Sabour	3.6	2.1	3.1	0.5
Dhangain	6.3	5.1	5.6	0.8
Tilaundha	2.7	2.2	2.3	0.7
Mean	4.4	3.2	3.6	—
	<i>1983 kharif</i>			
Patna	7.3	4.2	4.0	1.3
Pusa	2.7	3.1	2.5	0.8
Sabour	3.6	2.7	3.0	0.5
Dhangain	4.8	4.4	4.9	0.9
Tilaundha	2.7	2.9	3.1	0.4
Mean	4.2	3.5	3.5	—
	<i>1984 kharif</i>			
Patna	4.2	3.6	3.7	0.9
Sabour	3.6	2.9	2.9	0.4
Dhangain	5.5	3.8	4.1	1.0
Mean	4.4	3.4	3.6	—

Table 1. Grain yield and RTV infection of varieties, Aduthurai, India.

Variety	RTV infection (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
IET7301	21-30	2.1 b
IET7303	6-10	3.8 a
IET7573	41-60	1.3 c
IET7230	41-60	0.6 c
Co 43	31-40	2.2 b
IR20	31-40	0.6 c

7.5. N was applied 50% basal and 25% at tillering and panicle initiation. P and K were applied basally at 50 kg/ha.

IET7303 had least RTV infection and yielded highest, followed by IET7301. IR20 had severe RTV infection and low

Table 2. Effect of N on grain yield,^a Aduthurai, India.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	1.4 c
40	1.8 b
80	2.0 a
120	2.1 a

^aAverage of all varieties.

yield (Table 1). N level did not influence RTV, but significantly influenced grain yield. Highest yield was with 120 kg

N/ha, which was at par with yield at 80 kg N/ha (Table 2). N × varietal interaction was not significant. *ℓ*

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Seed dormancy in rice varieties

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Dormancy of seeds within the same panicle varies with spikelet position on the panicle. We studied within-panicle dormancy patterns of 10 popular kharif rices at ARS in 1982 kharif. Panicles were collected at harvest and divided equally into top, middle, and bottom parts. They were sown in soil and watered as necessary.

Dormancy was lowest in the top 1/3

Seed dormancy at different spikelet levels within rice panicles, Maruteru, India.

Variety	Dormant seeds (%)			Variety	Dormant seeds (%)		
	Top	Middle	Bottom		Top	Middle	Bottom
MTU5293	50	60	90	MTU5182	40	70	90
MTU2716	40	70	90	MTU2400	40	70	90
MTU2077	60	50	90	BPT11503	50	70	80
MTU4569	40	70	90	PLA1100	50	70	80
MTU5201	40	65	95	Mean	46	66.5	88.5
MTU2067	50	70	80	CD (5%): V : ns		P = 3	V × P : ns
				CV (%): 15.3			

of panicles and gradually increased in the middle and bottom parts (see table). This was attributed to the different age of seeds at different panicle levels.

Anthesis and fertilization occur in an acropetal succession; therefore the top spikelets are fertilized earliest and are oldest. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

High yielding, semidwarf, blast (BI)-resistant NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 for southern Andhra Pradesh

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NLR9672-96 and NLR27999 were developed for B1 resistance and suitable grain quality for southern Andhra Pradesh. NLR9672-96 is a secondary selection from NLR9672, from Bulk H/9 and Milekkunning. NLR27999 was selected from a segregating generation of RP31-49-2/BCP 1. Milekkunning and RP31-49-2 were parents for B1

Table 1. Yield attributes of NLR9672-96 and NLR27999, Nellore, India.

Variety	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle	1000-grain weight (g)
NLR27999	160-170	113	289	291	22
NLR9672-96	150-160	119	282	301	21
NLR9672	150-160	100	248	339	23
NLR9674	160-170	104	269	326	22

resistance. NLR9672-96 matures in 150-160 d and NLR27999 in 160-170 d. Both are weakly photoperiod sensitive and have short, bold grains with dirty brown glumes. Milled rice is white and translucent, and meets local consumer requirements. Threshability of both varieties is good, and both shed fewer

grains than locally grown NLR9672. Both have seed dormancy at maturity and lodging resistance. NLR9672-96 has a droopy flag leaf and NLR27999 an erect, medium flag leaf.

The varieties are moderately resistant to leaf and neck B1 and bacterial blight and resistant to brown planthopper.